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BUILDING AN ESP MANUAL THROUGH CORPUS INSIGHTS: BRIDGING RESEARCH AND CLASSROOM PRACTICE

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Abstract. *This paper reports on the process of developing an English for Specific Purposes (ESP) manual for students in the Oil and Gas field through the integration of corpus linguistics and learner-centered pedagogy. The study aimed to create discipline-specific teaching materials that reflect authentic professional discourse and align with learners' academic and occupational needs. The design process included several stages: conducting a needs analysis among students, examining practitioner-teachers' curricula, compiling and analyzing a specialized corpus using Sketch Engine, developing lessons and exercises, and validating the materials through classroom trials. Findings revealed a strong correspondence between the students' identified needs and the professional curriculum, confirming the relevance of selected topics. Corpus data ensured authenticity in language use and task design, while iterative classroom testing improved learner engagement and material effectiveness. The paper proposes a practical model of corpus-informed ESP manual development that bridges research insights with classroom practice.*

Key words: *corpus-informed materials, needs analysis, authenticity, material development, action research, classroom validation, learner engagement, professional communication.*

Introduction. The increasing demand for discipline-oriented English instruction has emphasized the need for authentic and up-to-date materials in English for Specific Purposes (ESP) contexts. In technical and professional domains such as Oil and Gas, students require access to realistic language input that mirrors professional communication in their field. However, many existing ESP textbooks fail to capture the linguistic and conceptual specificity of particular industries, often relying on generalized or outdated examples [2, 7]. This challenge calls for innovative approaches that connect linguistic research with classroom practice.

Corpus linguistics has become a powerful means of addressing this issue by providing empirical data about authentic language use [4, 15]. Corpus-informed materials allow teachers to identify discipline-specific vocabulary, phraseology, and discourse structures that reflect real communication patterns [8, 10]. The integration of corpus data into ESP instruction not only increases the authenticity of materials but also enhances learners' awareness of professional genres and communicative conventions [1, 6].

Nevertheless, developing corpus-based teaching materials requires careful alignment with learner needs and contextual realities. As Basturkmen [2] emphasizes, the success of ESP instruction depends on a systematic needs analysis and the extent to which materials mirror target-situation communication. It is also important to note that ESP teachers are primarily linguists rather than specialists in a particular professional sphere (in this case, Oil and Gas). Therefore, achieving complete certainty in the development of teaching materials that align with students' disciplinary knowledge is essential [3, 9].

For this reason, several key steps were undertaken in the development of a specialized manual for Oil and Gas undergraduates. First, a detailed needs analysis was conducted among students majoring in Oil and Gas Business, consistent with the learner-centered design approach advocated by Hutchinson and Waters [11]. Second, practitioner-teachers' curricula were examined to ensure topic relevance and authenticity. The results from both sources showed remarkable similarity, confirming the students' awareness of their professional linguistic needs.

Building on these findings, a specialized corpus was compiled and analyzed using the Sketch Engine platform [14], after which a series of lessons were designed and tested in the classroom. Each lesson underwent revision based on learner feedback and classroom observations, following the data-driven learning (DDL) cycle proposed by Johns [13]. This iterative process ensured that the final materials integrated authentic language data, pedagogical usability, and learner engagement.

This paper aims to describe this developmental process and illustrate how corpus insights and student-centered validation can jointly produce effective ESP materials. The study addresses the following research questions:

- How can corpus data contribute to the design of an ESP manual aligned with learners' professional and academic needs?
- What are the pedagogical outcomes of iterative classroom testing and revision in corpus-based material development?

Literature Review. Needs analysis has long been recognized as the cornerstone of ESP pedagogy, ensuring that language instruction accurately reflects the communicative demands of specific disciplines [11, 7, 2]. It involves identifying both target situation needs what learners must do with English in their professional field and learning needs what they must do to acquire the necessary competence effectively. Aligning ESP materials with learners' expectations and institutional curricula is therefore essential for maintaining relevance and motivation. In this regard, the combination of student questionnaires and the examination of practitioner-teachers' syllabi provides valuable insight into the overlap between learners' perceived needs and curricular goals, forming a data-informed foundation for material design.

Within this context, corpus linguistics provides an empirical foundation for analyzing authentic discourse and deriving pedagogically relevant linguistic patterns [4, 8]. In ESP, corpus-informed instruction enables the identification of discipline-specific vocabulary, phraseological patterns, and genre conventions that mirror authentic professional communication [6, 10]. The integration of corpus data into ESP material design enhances the authenticity and specificity of teaching content, allowing learners to engage with the language actually used in their professional domains. Despite these advantages, relatively few studies have documented the full process of corpus-informed material development from corpus compilation and analysis to classroom validation—particularly in technical disciplines such as Oil and Gas, where communicative practices are highly specialized [1, 8].

Bridging linguistic research with classroom practice represents an essential step in the advancement of ESP methodology. This integration aligns with the teacher-as-researcher paradigm [6], which emphasizes continuous refinement of materials through cycles of evaluation, reflection, and adaptation. Such an approach ensures that pedagogical outcomes are both theoretically sound and practically effective. The present study builds on this perspective, demonstrating how corpus analysis, systematic needs assessment, and classroom experimentation can converge to produce authentic and contextually relevant ESP materials that foster learners' professional communicative competence.

Methodology. This study employed an applied qualitative design with an emphasis on cyclic development. Each stage - needs analysis, corpus compilation, manual design, classroom trial, and revision was interconnected to ensure continuous feedback and improvement. The reflective, action research-inspired framework was adopted to bridge research and classroom practice in ESP.

The research was conducted at a technical university where English is offered as a subject for undergraduate students majoring in Oil and Gas Engineering. Participants included second- and third-year students, as well as practitioner-teachers responsible for technical subjects. The initial phase focused on identifying learners' professional language needs. Second- and third-year students received questionnaires designed to determine which professional topics were most relevant to their future careers. Informal interviews complemented the questionnaires, allowing students to specify key themes and terminology drawn from their specialty courses. At the same time, the official syllabi of practitioner-teachers were analyzed to determine the core content of Oil and Gas subjects. The comparison revealed a near-complete correspondence between the two sources, confirming that the

topics prioritized by students such as *safety procedures*, *storage tanks*, *types of pipelines*, *compressor stations*, and *reservoir management*, matched those emphasized in their academic programs. This alignment served as the foundation for lesson selection and material design.

To ensure linguistic authenticity, a specialized corpus was compiled using the Sketch Engine platform [1]. The corpus consisted of texts sourced from scientific articles, technical manuals, textbooks, web pages, and online publications related to the Oil and Gas sector. After cleaning and tagging, the data were analyzed for word frequency, collocations, and key terms. The most frequent lexical bundles, including oil *recovery process*, *safety*, *pressure maintenance system*, and *crude oil*, were identified and subsequently incorporated into vocabulary exercises and reading materials. Phraseological and grammatical patterns typical of professional discourse informed both the structure of the tasks and the selection of illustrative texts.

Based on the findings from the needs analysis and corpus study, the manual was designed as a sequence of lessons organized thematically. Each unit combined reading, vocabulary, and writing sections, with tasks derived from authentic corpus-based texts. Frequency-based word lists supported the learning of specialized terminology, while concordance-based activities encouraged students to infer meaning from contextual usage. Recognizing the importance of visual comprehension in technical communication, photographs and diagrams were carefully selected for each topic. To confirm their relevance and accuracy, third- and fourth-year students were consulted and asked to evaluate whether the visuals accurately represented real-world processes and equipment. This participatory approach not only ensured contextual precision but also enhanced learner engagement and ownership of the material.

Here, examples from the developed manual are presented to illustrate the structure and design of the lessons, including sample vocabulary exercises, reading passages, and visual components such as photographs and diagrams used in the Oil and Gas context.

LESSON 5. TYPES OF PIPELINES

Starter

1. Answer the question:

- What types of pipelines do you know?
- What are they used for?

Grammar task

5. Complete the missing spaces with the words given in the box.

gathering cutting tapping used refined

1. For starters, they are purpose-built to carry commodities like oil, gas and _____ products.
2. This pit will be used to dispose of rock cuttings and _____ drilling mud.
3. Pipelines can refer to _____ systems (wellhead to processing facilities), transmission lines (supply areas to markets), or distribution pipelines.

Vocabulary

6. Look at the words in column A and match them with column B.

- | | |
|-----------------------------|------------------------------|
| 1 handle (v) | A. вести себя |
| 2 block valve stations (n) | B. мощность |
| 3 hill (n) | C. соответствующий |
| 4 behave (v) | D. возвращаться |
| 5 specific gravity (n) | E. холм |
| 6 experience (v) | F. случайные разливы |
| 7 pressure drops uphill (n) | G. станции линейной арматуры |
| 8 downhill (n) | H. станции запорной арматуры |
| 9 require (v) | I. разрыв трубопровода |
| 10 capacity (n) | J. тормозная станция |

Reading

3. Read and translate the text paying particular attention to the bold words.

PIPELINE CORROSION

Pipe corrosion occurs when water (a corrosive electrolyte) combines with **oxygen** on two metal pipe surfaces, which **triggers** an electrochemical process or electrical connection between the metal areas. Corrosion **requires** four elements, anode, cathode, metallic path, and electrolyte to occur. The first three elements are typically **present** and the **addition** of the electrolyte from the environment completes the corrosion cell. Higher

Before publication, each lesson underwent classroom testing with target learners. Students were asked to complete exercises, provide comments on clarity and usefulness, and discuss the relevance of the materials to their academic and professional studies. After each trial, revisions were made based on the collected feedback modifying instructions, adjusting text difficulty, and replacing examples when necessary. This iterative process of validation resulted in the gradual refinement of each lesson. The development of the first lesson, for instance, went through multiple revisions before reaching its final form, which clearly demonstrated the effectiveness of direct classroom evidence in the design of ESP materials.

Results. The implementation and classroom testing of the corpus-informed manual provided valuable insights into its pedagogical effectiveness and learners' engagement with authentic disciplinary language. The data collected from classroom observations, student feedback, and post-lesson discussions revealed notable improvements in both students' linguistic competence and their confidence in handling subject-specific texts.

The results demonstrated that corpus-driven materials encouraged students to approach professional vocabulary more analytically. Learners reported that frequency-based word lists and concordance activities helped them notice recurring patterns and collocations in authentic Oil and Gas discourse. In classroom observations, students displayed a growing ability to infer meaning from context and to use terminology accurately in written and oral tasks. This was particularly evident in the later lessons, where learners began to employ target lexical bundles such as oil recovery process and pressure maintenance system spontaneously in their written summaries and oral explanations.

Feedback collected through reflective questionnaires indicated that the majority of students perceived the manual as both relevant and motivating. They appreciated that the materials incorporated real professional content rather than generic texts, which made language learning more purposeful. Many participants emphasized the usefulness of visual elements photographs, diagrams, and process schematics which aided comprehension of technical descriptions. Comments such as "It was really useful and interesting," "I liked all the tasks," and "More terminology could be included" highlighted the perceived authenticity and accessibility of the manual.

The iterative process of classroom validation led to gradual refinement of the lessons. Based on feedback, certain reading passages were simplified, task instructions clarified, and visuals expanded to include more field-specific imagery. These revisions contributed to higher student satisfaction in subsequent trials. A comparative evaluation of the first and final versions of selected lessons revealed increased task clarity, smoother progression from receptive to productive skills, and improved alignment between linguistic input and professional content.

Overall, the results suggest that the integration of corpus insights into ESP material design effectively bridges research and classroom practice. Students demonstrated both linguistic gains and a stronger connection between English learning and their disciplinary studies. The corpus-informed manual not only supported the acquisition of specialized terminology but also fostered independent learning strategies and professional language awareness among Oil and Gas undergraduates.

Discussion. The study demonstrates that corpus-informed material design can effectively bridge research and classroom practice in ESP contexts. By grounding topic selection in both needs analysis and corpus evidence, the developed manual achieved a high level of authenticity and alignment with learners' academic and professional realities. The findings support previous research suggesting that corpus-based approaches enhance vocabulary acquisition and discourse awareness [8, 5], while offering a distinctive contribution in the form of a participatory, iterative model for ESP material creation.

Moreover, the study illustrates that a linguist without a specialized technical background can successfully design domain-specific materials through systematic consultation with students and subject experts. The integration of corpus data compensates for disciplinary limitations, ensuring both linguistic precision and contextual validity. Iterative classroom trials served as a continuous feedback mechanism, transforming the material development process into a dynamic form of action research. These outcomes reaffirm the idea that ESP practitioners can function as researchers who innovate within their own teaching contexts, contributing simultaneously to pedagogical practice and applied linguistic inquiry.

Conclusion. This study explored how corpus insights can inform the development of an ESP manual that bridges research and classroom practice. Using a cyclic, qualitative framework that included needs analysis, corpus compilation, material design, and classroom validation, it demonstrated that corpus-informed pedagogy enhances authenticity and contextual relevance in ESP instruction. The integration of corpus data allowed the manual to reflect the linguistic and thematic realities of the Oil and Gas field, while iterative testing ensured pedagogical effectiveness and learner engagement.

The findings confirm that even without deep technical expertise, ESP practitioners can design domain-specific materials through collaboration with students and subject specialists. Corpus-informed material design thus serves as a practical model of action research, linking linguistic evidence with real classroom needs. Future studies could further examine measurable learning outcomes and extend this approach to other professional disciplines.

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